

Project poster and briefing leaflet

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This document requires the following approvals:

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Executive summary

A project poster (PDF) and a project briefing (two-page summary in PDF format) have been prepared and will be translated in the 5 languages of the regions in focus, for partners to use in conferences and regional workshops to explain and raise awareness of the project. Deliverable D7.4 includes a copy of the branded documents.

A high-definition version of the poster and the leaflet have been sent to all partners and have been made available to the public via the project's website <https://pilotstrategy.eu/>.

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1. [PilotSTRATEGY poster]

CO₂ geological storage in strategic territories

Building a low-carbon, climate-resilient future: secure, clean and efficient energy

Coordinator: Dr Fernanda M.L. Veloso, BRGM (f.veloso@brgm.fr)

Abstract

PilotSTRATEGY focuses on advancing understanding of deep saline aquifers (DSAs) for geological CO₂ storage in five European industrial regions to support large-scale carbon capture and storage (CCS), a critical technology in the net-zero transition. Our research team of 16 scientific and industrial partners will build on the STRATEGY CCUS project which, among other things, identified a need to accelerate development of CO₂ storage.

DSAs have much promise for CO₂ storage, but are not well studied. PilotSTRATEGY will investigate DSAs in detail in three regions: Paris Basin (France), Lusitanian Basin (Portugal) and Ebro Basin (Spain). At the end of our five-year project, the level of site characterisation in these regions will be sufficient for a final investment decision to be made.

In two further regions, West Macedonia (Greece) and Upper Silesia (Poland), PilotSTRATEGY will update, and increase confidence in, understanding of DSA storage resources. This will enable these regions to start planning development of their CO₂ storage resources.

Recognising the social challenges of implementing geological CO₂ storage, PilotSTRATEGY will develop public engagement strategies and include regional stakeholders and local communities in project implementation.

Our Regions

1. Paris Basin, France

- Industrial facility already capturing ~300 kt/CO₂ per year
- Storage resources within Kuiper & Dogger Formations
- Kuiper-identified effective storage capacity Tier 2 of 0.220t
- Dogger-identified theoretical storage capacity Tier 1 of 200Mt

2. Lusitanian Basin, Portugal

- Includes CO₂ similitars in the Setúbal - Figueira da Foz axis, could accept CO₂ from Lisbon region
- CO₂ effective DSA storage capacity: 0.290t onshore Tier 2; theoretic capacity 2.860t offshore Tier 1
- Social acceptance will be factor in storage pilot's location

3. Ebro Basin, Spain

- Region includes Tarragona industrial area
- Onshore & offshore CO₂ storage potential exists within 100km radius
- Onshore CO₂ storage estimated at up to 0.850t Tier 2 of capacity by STRATEGY CCUS

4. West Macedonia, Greece

- Region covers Kozani and Ptolemais industrial areas
- Storage resource provided by the Meschallens Trough
- CO₂ storage in DSA estimated at 1.60t Tier 1 in STRATEGY CCUS

5. Upper Silesia, Poland

- Region includes industrial areas of Katowice, Rybnik and Bełżyn
- Poland's most industrialised region, with 16 coal mines and 75W of power generation
- CO₂ storage capacity of 0.050t in uneconomic coal beds and of 0.30t in DSA

6. Germany (supporting country)

7. UK (supporting country)

Key expected impacts

Impact	PilotSTRATEGY Actions/Outputs
Detailed geo-characterisation	- Conceptual Geological Model for five target regions - New data including 3D active & passive seismic - Characterisation (geological, geochemical & geomechanical) at field & sample scale for five regions
Safe storage sites; numerical simulations of CO ₂ fate and its impact in subsurface	- Optimisation of well location and CO ₂ injection rate by numerical simulations for four regions - Short & long-term CO ₂ fate in subsurface for five regions - Pressure, geochemical & geomechanical impacts for four regions - Impacts in near wellbore linked to injectivity issues - Fault/fractures and caprock integrity for four regions
Development plans for safe storage sites in three most promising regions	- Pre-FEED level development plan for CO ₂ storage sites in France, Portugal & Spain - Guidelines for risk identification in storage site development & assessment, including mitigation & preventive measures
Facilitate subsequent storage permit applications to help kick start CCS/CCUS	- Complete documentation for injection permits for France, Portugal & Spain in local languages - Guidelines & road maps for permit submission, tailored to France, Portugal & Spain, in local languages - Overview for Greece & Poland
Baseline storage cost estimates	- Class 4 cost estimates for France, Portugal & Spain - Creation of cost estimate database for future CO ₂ storage sites in other European countries
Increased public awareness	- Eight surveys in five target countries for public acceptance mapping - 10 workshops and engagement activities, aimed at citizens, media & policy makers, close to proposed pilot locations - Five Regional Stakeholders Committees - Project dissemination: webinars, media and social media; clear, accessible information on project website
Laying groundwork for CCS/CCUS operational stage in the mid-2020s	- Complete studies for pre-FID in three main regions, including pre-FEED design - Techno-economic pre-feasibility studies for CCUS in all five regions - Engage key stakeholders on implementation of future storage facilities

The five-year PilotSTRATEGY project, which commenced in 2020, has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101022664.

2. [PilotSTRATEGY project briefing (2pp)]

PilotSTRATEGY is an ambitious five-year international research project on the use of deep saline aquifers for geological storage of CO₂ to support development of large-scale carbon capture and storage (CCS), a critical technology in the net-zero transition.

Building on the findings of the STRATEGY CCUS project, PilotSTRATEGY will carry out detailed studies in three promising regions in France, Portugal and Spain. We will also enhance knowledge of CO₂ storage options in Greece and Poland.

Objectives

- 🎯 Focus on deep saline aquifers which promise large capacity for CO₂ storage
- 🎯 Support safe and effective storage pilots
- 🎯 Engage with citizens & stakeholders; evaluate factors affecting CCS acceptance

1. Paris Basin, France

- 🎯 Industrial facility already capturing > 300 kt/CO₂ per year
- 🎯 Storage resources within Keuper & Dogger Formations
- 🎯 Keuper: identified effective storage capacity Tier 2 of 0.22Gt
- 🎯 Dogger: identified theoretical storage capacity Tier 1 of 0.2Gt

2. Lusitanian Basin, Portugal

- 🎯 Includes CO₂ emitters in the Setúbal – Figueira da Foz axis; could accept CO₂ from Lisbon region
- 🎯 CO₂ effective DSA storage capacity: 0.26Gt onshore Tier 2; theoretic capacity 2.86GT offshore Tier 1
- 🎯 Social acceptance will be factor in storage pilot's location

3. Ebro Basin, Spain

- 🎯 Region includes Tarragona industrial area
- 🎯 Onshore & offshore CO₂ storage potential exists within 100km radius
- 🎯 Onshore CO₂ storage estimated at up to 0.85Gt Tier 2 of capacity

5. Upper Silesia, Poland

- 🎯 Region includes industrial areas of Katowice, Rybnik and Bedzin
- 🎯 Poland's most industrialised region, with 16 coal mines and 7GW of power generation
- 🎯 CO₂ storage capacity of 0.015Gt in uneconomic coal beds and of 0.1GT In DSA

4. West Macedonia, Greece

- 🎯 Region covers Kozani and Ptolemaida industrial areas
- 🎯 Storage resource provided by the Mesohellenic Trough
- 🎯 CO₂ storage in DSA estimated at 1.16Gt Tier 1 (theoretical)

6. Germany (supporting country)

7. UK (supporting country)

Work Packages

Led by France's BRGM, our research team combines the skills and experience of 16 scientific and industrial partners from seven European countries.

WP2 Geo-characterisation

Assembling, acquiring and interpreting geological data

WP3 Simulation

Assessment of site storage capacity and integrity

WP4 Pilot Development

Development concepts and pre-FEED for proposed pilots (Ebro, Lusitanian and Paris Basins)

WP5 Safety

Ensuring proposed pilots meet the best safety and performance standards

WP6 Social Acceptance

Investigating societal acceptance and public engagement

WP7 Communication and Impact

Increasing the visibility and impact of the project

Why is this project important?

- ❶ Carbon capture and storage (CCS) – whereby CO₂ is captured from large emitters for permanent underground storage – is pivotal to Europe's climate commitments. Meeting the challenge will depend on sufficient geological CO₂ storage becoming available in time.
- ❷ PilotSTRATEGY will help develop CO₂ storage capacity and build confidence in CCS. Further research, policy support, and building public acceptance are critical to ensure CCS becomes a feasible climate mitigation option for local industries and local communities.
- ❸ We are focusing on deep saline aquifers – porous rock formations filled with brine several kilometres below ground – which promise a large capacity for storing captured CO₂, but which have been under-researched for CCS until now.

The five-year PilotSTRATEGY project, which commenced in 2021, has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101022664.

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3. Conclusion

The project poster and the project briefing have been developed to be used in conferences, meetings and public events by PilotSTRATEGY partners and to be accessible by the public via the project website.

